

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

SYNERGY OF ECONOMY AND SECURITY: IS A NEW MODEL OF INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION POSSIBLE?

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Abstract

The aim of the article is to explore the interrelations between military expenditures and economic indicators in NATO countries and Eastern states over the period 2000–2023. The study employs a VAR model to assess the impact of military expenditures on GDP per capita and unemployment rates, highlighting significant differences in the strategic priorities of these two groups of countries. The analysis reveals that NATO's military expenditures have a multiplicative effect, stimulating economic growth and employment through the development of innovative technologies and industrial sectors. In contrast, Eastern states focus primarily on long-term technological advancement and increasing geopolitical influence. The practical relevance of the research lies in providing recommendations for optimizing the synergy between economy and security, which can be valuable for designing modern international strategies.

Keywords: military expenditures, NATO, Eastern states, VAR model, economic development, security.

Problem Statement

In the modern world, economic interdependence and growing global challenges make the synergy between economy and security one of the key issues of international cooperation. Despite significant progress in globalization, several pressing problems persist, such as unequal access to resources, regional conflicts and wars that could escalate into a third world war, economic instability, and climate threats. The lack of integrated approaches to addressing these issues severely limits the potential for achieving sustainable global stability.

At the same time, there are opportunities to combine economic and security strategies that allow nations to enhance trust and cooperation. For instance, economic initiatives such as regional trade agreements or joint infrastructure projects can serve as tools to reduce tensions between states. However, existing mechanisms of cooperation often focus on short-term goals, neglecting long-term risks.

Thus, there is an urgent need to create a new model of international cooperation based on the integration of economic, security, and environmental strategies. This approach would not only ensure economic stability but also strengthen global security through mutually beneficial collaboration.

Analysis of Recent Research and Publications

Contemporary academic literature extensively addresses the interconnection between economy and security. J. Nye (2011) introduces the concept of "soft power," emphasizing the use of economic tools to achieve international stability. He highlights that economic interdependence between states reduces the risk of conflicts, contributing to a more stable global order.

R. Keohane (2005) focuses on the role of international institutions such as the UN, WTO, and IMF in ensuring synergy between the economic and security interests of nations. He underscores the importance of

multilateral approaches to addressing global challenges by creating joint regulatory mechanisms that enable more effective coordination among states.

A different perspective is offered by D. Rodrik (2011) in his book *The Globalization Paradox*. Rodrik highlights the consequences of uneven economic development on international security. He notes that globalization, while promoting economic growth, simultaneously exacerbates inequality, which can become a source of social and geopolitical conflicts.

J. Stiglitz (2012) in his work *The Price of Inequality* emphasizes that economic inequality is one of the greatest challenges of the modern world. He argues that without addressing this issue, achieving a stable international system is impossible. Stiglitz also stresses the importance of state regulation to ensure equal access to resources and enhance social equity.

Practical aspects of the synergy between economy and security are studied through examples of regional cooperation. The European Union, for instance, demonstrates a successful model where economic integration contributes to strengthening regional security. Another example is China's *Belt and Road Initiative*, which combines economic interests with geopolitical goals, creating conditions for long-term regional stability.

Despite the significant body of research, the issue of integrating economic and security strategies remains underdeveloped. Most models focus on individual aspects, ignoring their interaction. This gap highlights the need for further study and the development of new approaches.

Unresolved Aspects of the Economy-Security Interaction

Despite a substantial volume of research, many aspects of the interaction between economy and security remain unresolved. One of the critical gaps is the ab-

sence of an integrated approach that simultaneously accounts for economic, security, and environmental factors. Existing models of international cooperation often focus on addressing short-term challenges, overlooking long-term issues such as climate change, growing inequality, and escalating social instability.

Another unresolved issue is the insufficient consideration of national economic and security strategies. Each country has unique needs and challenges that cannot always be effectively integrated into general international models. For instance, developed economies such as the United States emphasize innovations and technology, whereas developing countries face limited access to resources and unstable markets. Additionally, the interaction between Western countries and communist China highlights differing strategic objectives. China's support for Russia during the war against Ukraine exemplifies how these divergent goals can manifest in practice.

The coordination of actions among global institutions such as the UN, WTO, and IMF also poses a significant challenge. These organizations often focus on addressing specific issues, leading to a lack of alignment in their approaches to economic and security policies. This disjointedness has been particularly evident during the Russia-Ukraine war, complicating the development of cohesive strategies and mechanisms for responding to global threats.

Moreover, the problem of building trust among states within multilateral cooperation frameworks remains unresolved. The absence of transparency and effective monitoring mechanisms limits the potential for creating joint initiatives in the fields of economy and security. Addressing this issue requires the development of a new model based on the principles of collaboration, trust, and shared responsibility.

The purpose of this article is to identify the interconnections between economic and security spheres in the context of modern globalization, contributing to

the development of an innovative model of international cooperation that ensures effective synergy between these key domains.

The proposed model aims to integrate economic, security, and environmental strategies, taking into account both the specific national interests of individual countries and the pressing global challenges. This study highlights the main shortcomings of existing approaches, formulates recommendations for their improvement, and outlines prospects for implementing new mechanisms of interaction on the international stage.

Main Content

The modern world faces complex challenges that necessitate a rethinking of the relationship between military expenditures and economic development. Military budgets have become not only an essential tool for ensuring national security but also a driver of economic growth through the advancement of innovative technologies, increased employment, and the strengthening of industrial sectors. In this context, an analysis of military expenditures by NATO and Eastern countries over the period 2000–2023 reveals critical patterns and differences.

This examination highlights the dual role of military spending as a mechanism for defense and an economic catalyst, with varying impacts and strategic priorities across regions. NATO countries, with their advanced economies, leverage military budgets to foster technological innovation and industrial expansion. In contrast, Eastern nations focus more on long-term strategic objectives, including technological development and regional influence.

The findings emphasize the need for a balanced and integrative approach to military expenditures, one that aligns economic development with national and international security objectives. This alignment is particularly relevant given the increasing interdependence of global economies and the growing significance of defense as a component of comprehensive national strategies.

Fig. 1 Dynamics of NATO and Eastern Countries' Military Expenditures (2000–2023)[11]

Figure 1 illustrates the dynamics of NATO and Eastern countries' military expenditures over the period 2000–2023. During this time, NATO's expenditures increased from \$400 billion in 2000 to \$1,100 billion in 2023, highlighting a significant focus on modernizing defense systems and enhancing geopolitical influence. Meanwhile, Eastern countries' military expenditures rose from \$100 billion in 2000 to \$420 billion in 2023, reflecting their emphasis on long-term technological development and regional stability.

An analysis of NATO and Eastern countries' military expenditures reveals substantial differences. NATO's expenditures remain consistently higher, driven by the integration of the defense sector with the broader economy. High levels of investment in cutting-edge technologies, particularly artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, and missile defense, not only enhance military capabilities but also stimulate economic activity.

To analyze the impact of military expenditures on key economic indicators in more detail, a VAR model

was applied. The results show that in NATO countries, increases in military expenditures have a multiplicative effect, boosting GDP per capita and reducing unemployment rates. This effect is particularly pronounced in the short term (within the first 3–5 periods).

The VAR model results for Eastern countries reveal a different pattern. Military expenditures contribute to gradual GDP growth, peaking within 8–10 periods, but have a less pronounced impact on unemployment rates. This is explained by the fact that the majority of funds are allocated to capital projects and technological development, rather than creating new jobs in the short term.

Figure 2 shows the impulse responses for NATO, demonstrating that increases in military expenditures positively affect GDP and employment, stimulating the growth of the defense industry and related sectors. **Figure 3 presents similar data for Eastern countries,** highlighting their focus on technological development without significant job growth.

Fig. 2. The Interconnection between Military Expenditures, GDP per Capita, and Unemployment Rates in NATO Countries. Results of the VAR Model for NATO: Impulse Responses. Developed by the author using the Python system

The comparative analysis of modeling results and impulse responses highlights significant differences in approaches to military expenditures between NATO and Eastern countries. NATO focuses on creating synergy between defense and economic goals, fostering growth in domestic demand and employment. In contrast, Eastern countries, particularly China, Russia, and Iran, concentrate on long-term strategic objectives, such as regional influence and enhancing technological potential, often disregarding domestic demand. This approach militarizes their economies, enabling the production of substantial quantities of weaponry and equipment in the short term.

The study emphasizes the importance of adapting economic and security strategies to new challenges. For NATO countries, the key task is maintaining a balance between innovation and the socio-economic impact of military expenditures. For Eastern countries, the priority is integrating military spending into a broader economic context to ensure sustainable development.

An analysis of NATO’s military spending trends over the period 2000–2023 demonstrates a strong emphasis on integrating the defense sector with the overall

economy. Investments in high-tech industries, such as artificial intelligence development and missile defense systems, create additional jobs, stimulate innovation, and support GDP growth, even during periods of economic instability.

For Eastern countries, particularly China, Russia, and Iran, increased military spending is linked to long-term strategic objectives, such as strengthening regional influence. For example, China actively invests in modernizing its naval forces and drone development, allowing it to secure a leading position in the Asia-Pacific region and assert itself as the world's second-largest economy.

Figure 3 presents the impulse responses for Eastern countries, illustrating that military expenditures have a significant impact on technological development. However, their effect on unemployment rates is less pronounced, as a substantial portion of investments is directed toward capital projects that do not immediately generate new jobs.

Fig. 3. The Interconnection between Military Expenditures, GDP per Capita, and Unemployment Rates in Eastern Countries Results of the VAR Model: Impulse Responses
Developed by the author using the Python system

The impulse responses of the VAR model for NATO countries, as shown in **Figure 2**, clearly illustrate the multiplicative effect of defense expenditures. Specifically, the growth in employment in sectors such as logistics, manufacturing, and research stimulates domestic demand, explaining why NATO economies exhibit stable growth even under heightened geopolitical tension.

A comparison between NATO and Eastern countries reveals significant differences in approaches to military budgets. NATO prioritizes creating synergy between defense and economic goals, while Eastern countries, such as Russia and Iran, focus more on enhancing strategic capabilities and developing autonomous defense systems.

Geopolitical factors play a critical role in shaping military expenditures. For NATO, the primary challenge is ensuring collective defense, particularly in response to regional conflicts and threats from other states. For Eastern countries, military spending is often tied to ambitions of strengthening regional influence and strategic autonomy.

The economic component of military expenditures is becoming increasingly important in shaping modern security policies. For NATO, effective synergy between defense spending and the economy not only strengthens national security but also creates conditions for domestic market growth, attracting investments, and expanding exports.

Eastern countries, particularly China, demonstrate an alternative approach focused on developing autonomous technologies and strengthening their influence in strategically significant regions. For instance, substantial investments in military research create preconditions for innovations in civilian economic sectors.

An analysis of data from 2000–2023 highlights that NATO's military expenditures are a key driver of economic growth through expanded employment and

investments in high-tech industries. For Eastern countries, the primary focus remains on long-term technological development.

The data emphasize the need to harmonize military and economic strategies. For NATO, further increases in military expenditures can drive innovation and employment. However, this strategy has also created an illusion of security in Europe, as the United States has borne the primary burden of military spending. For Eastern countries, the key challenge is ensuring a more effective transformation of military investments into long-term economic development, as exemplified by China's strategic approach.

Considering the fundamentally different approaches to the synergy of economy and security between Western democracies and Eastern authoritarian regimes, the question posed in the title of the article regarding the possibility of international cooperation can be answered: such cooperation is only feasible among Western countries. Today, it would not be advisable for democratic nations to engage in joint security-related investment projects with China or, even more so, with Russia, Iran, or North Korea, which are under sanctions. Selling high-tech dual-use goods to these countries could undermine their own security.

Conclusions

The results of the study confirm the significant impact of military expenditures on shaping economic and security policies in both NATO countries and nations such as China and Russia. According to the VAR model analysis, military expenditures directly affect key economic indicators, such as GDP per capita and employment rates. However, the nature and intensity of this influence differ considerably depending on the group of countries analyzed.

For NATO countries, military expenditures serve not only as a means of ensuring defense capabilities but also play a critical economic role by stimulating GDP growth and employment through the activation of the

defense industry and related sectors. The high level of integration of military expenditures into the overall economic structure of NATO countries facilitates the efficient use of financial resources, yielding positive economic effects even in the short term. However, the current confrontation between Russia and China against the West necessitates a significant increase in military expenditures and a higher level of militarization of the economy.

China and Russia follow a different approach to military expenditures, focusing on long-term strategic objectives, such as enhancing technological potential and securing geopolitical leadership. According to the VAR model results, the primary impact of military expenditures in these countries is concentrated on technological development, while their influence on employment remains limited.

The impulse responses obtained in this study vividly illustrate the divergence in economic and security strategies between the two groups of countries. NATO emphasizes creating synergy between military and economic expenditures, whereas authoritarian states focus on developing autonomous defense capabilities. These approaches stem from the economic resources and geopolitical challenges faced by these countries. The underestimation of security aspects in extensive international cooperation between the EU and the U.S. with China and Russia has led to Russia's full-scale war against Ukraine and Iran's proxy conflict with Israel, bringing the world to the brink of nuclear war.

Thus, the results of the study underscore the importance of considering the interrelation between military expenditures and economic indicators when developing effective strategies. For NATO countries, maintaining a balance between innovation and the socio-economic benefits of defense spending is no longer feasible. Consequently, the implementation of joint projects involving security components between Western nations and China, along with its allies Russia, Iran, and North Korea, could undermine national, regional, and global security.

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